

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE USE AND TRANSLATION OF ENGLISH MEDICAL TERMS

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Abstract. This article discusses the translation and significance of medical terms and phrases used in English. It provides information on the structural and morphological significance of English medical terms, their role in medicine and their specific features. In addition, the specific role and models of English phrases used in communicative communication in medicine are presented based on examples and analysis.

Key words: medical term, structure, prefix, suffix, communicative communication, internal organs, medical treatment.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilida qo'llaniladigan tibbiy terminlar va jumalarning tarjimasi va ahamiyati to'g'risida fikr yuritilgan. Unda inglizcha tibbiy terminlarning struktur va morfologik ahamiyati, tibbiyotdagi o'rni va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari borasida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Bundan tashqari tibbiyotda kommunikativ muloqoda ishlatiladigan inglizcha frazalarning o'ziga xos o'rni va modellari misollar va tahlillar asosida keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tibbiy atama, struktura, prefiks, suffiks, kommunikativ muloqot, ichki organlar, tibbiy muolaja.

English medical terms are terms used in the field of scientific medicine, often used by professional specialists. These terms are used to accurately describe various diseases, medical procedures, organs, surgical procedures, drugs, and other medical concepts. English medical terms are often borrowed from Latin and Greek, because these languages have been widely used in medical science since ancient times.

Structure of medical terms. English medical terms are often formed based on the following structures:

Prefix (prefixes) – Affixes are parts of a medical word that either expand or narrow the meaning of the word. For example, "hypo-" (less), "hyper-" (more), "sub-" (under).

1. **Root (main root)** – The main word, i.e. the parts that describe a specific disease or condition. For example, "cardi-" (heart), "neuro-" (neuron or nervous system).
2. **Suffix (suffixes)** – The endings at the end of medical words that complete or describe their meaning. For example, "-itis" (inflammation), "-ectomy" (cut or removal).

Cardiologist – A doctor who studies the heart. The word is formed from the combination of "cardi-" (heart) and "-ologist" (specialist).

1. **Appendectomy** – Surgical removal of a lung abscess. "Appendix" (lung) and "-ectomy" (removal) added.
2. **Hypertension** – High blood pressure. Made up of the words "Hyper-" (high) and "-tension" (pressure).
3. **Neurosurgery** – Neurosurgery, i.e. surgical procedures involving the nervous system. The words "neuro-" (nervous system) and "-surgery" (surgery) are combined.

The importance of medical terminology. The accuracy and correct use of medical terms is very important, as they facilitate communication between specialists and allow for the effective treatment of diseases or conditions. In medicine, the use of incorrect words or misunderstandings can seriously affect the health of a patient. Also, English medical terms are used in different parts of the world, which further strengthens communication between global medical professionals.

The widespread use of English in the field of medicine is of great importance today on a global scale. English has become the main language for many scientific studies, technical and clinical documents. The correct and accurate translation of medical terminology plays a vital role in providing the necessary care for patients. Therefore, the translation of English medical terms and their correct approach are of great importance.

There are several difficulties in translating medical terms from English into other languages. Each language has its own grammatical structure, ways of defining terms, and cultural perspectives. English medical terms often need to be precise and accurate, as they directly affect the lives and health of patients. Translators need to convey these terms in a clear, understandable, and language-appropriate manner.

For example, the English term "hypertension" requires special nuances when translating into other languages. When translating this term, its medical meaning, as well as medical concepts specific to each language, are taken into account.

English medical terms must be clear, concise, and reliable. They are often words derived from Latin, so they can be similar in different languages. For example, words such as "cardiology" and "oncology" are often preserved in the same form in different languages when translated from English because these terms are used as a common concept internationally.

However, not every medical term is always translated in the same way. In some cases, these terms differ depending on local traditions, medical styles, and culture. For example, the translation of the term "diabetes mellitus" (diabetes) may be the same depending on the medical tradition, but in some languages it may be interpreted differently.

The main issues to consider when translating English medical terms are as follows.

1. **Taking context into account.** The translation of a medical term should be done based on the context. Each term can be interpreted differently depending on the clinical situation or laboratory data.
2. **Clarity of terminology.** Translators must maintain the precise medical meaning of a term. In the medical field, an incorrect translation can harm a patient's health.
3. **Taking into account cultural differences.** The way medical terms are understood and accepted may differ from region to region or language to language, so it is important to pay attention to cultural nuances when translating.

Furthermore, speaking English in medicine is essential to ensure effective communication between doctors, medical staff and patients. Let's take a look at some of the key English vocabulary and terms used in medicine:

1. Greeting the patient: Hello, how are you feeling today?, Can you tell me what brings you here today?, Please take a seat.

2. Conducting the examination: I'm going to check your temperature, Let me listen to your heart and lungs, Take a deep breath.

3. If the patient talks about symptoms: When did the pain start?, Is the pain constant or does it come and go?, On a scale of 1 to 10, how severe is the pain?.

4. Diagnosis and treatment: You need an X-ray to better understand the problem, We will prescribe some medication to help you feel better, You may need surgery to treat this condition.

5. During the treatment process: You need to follow these instructions carefully, If you experience any side effects, please let me know, This procedure will help reduce the pain.

6. Ending the consultation: Do you have any other questions?, Please come back for a follow-up appointment next week, Take care, and I hope you feel better soon.

Such expressions are used in medicine when communicating with patients and can be helpful to doctors and nurses working in the medical field.

Conclusion. The translation of English medical terms is essential for effective communication and collaboration in the medical field. Care and accuracy are required when translating, as this directly affects the patient's diagnosis, treatment process and clinical outcomes. Translators must consider a wide range of scientific sources, medical dictionaries and expert recommendations to ensure accurate and precise translation of medical terms. Also, taking into account language differences and cultural characteristics helps to ensure the correct transmission of each medical term.

English medical terms are essential for the development of medical science and for more effective international cooperation. These words help to clearly express medical concepts and are an essential tool for proper communication between different specialists.

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